

A HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVE ON THE MISUSE OF POWER IN ORWELL'S ANIMAL FARM

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ABSTRACT

It is normal to witness politicians exploiting ordinary people as a result of the leader's poor use of absolute authority and the people's silence. Knowledge and education appear to lead to total power, culminating in the pain and persecution of simple and ignorant people in the Soviet Union. The majority of people do not understand the terminology utilized in Animal Farm, which creates a danger through numerous concepts and rules. This allowed the wealthy to abuse people for their selfish interests and engage in illegal activities. As a result of the use of ambiguous language and the deployment of terror tactics, they were able to persuade others, and then they developed lies in the interests of leaders. However, because of their simplicity, the others were readily persuaded, whereas power could be used to serve the entire people of the Soviet Union. The paper analyzes the research using a historical method.

George Orwell is the best novelist in modern English literature who depicts a political time in the middle of the twentieth century. Novels of the modern era were inspired by emerging realities and political issues. Novelists are unable to stop societal shifts and innovate new methods. Though Animal Farm is an allegory based on the Russian Revolution and the advent of Stalin, George Orwell believed that it is truly an investigation of all political uprisings and rebellions and how political systems overrun human freedom.

Orwell received criticism for his two outstanding novels, Animal Farm and Nineteen Eighty-Four. He saw these works as useful tools for arguing against political points in dystopian events and illustrating a bleak future for humanity based on the fight against totalitarianism and the immorality of power. However, Animal Farm was presented by Orwell as a fairy tale.

Orwell was a writer whose writing had an impact on people's attitudes toward political events. Orwell's writing developed at a time when society was struggling and anticipating the Second World War. George Orwell wrote both Animal Farm and Nineteen Eighty-Four, which

were extraordinarily successful arguments for contrast to dictatorship and awareness of social inequality. He considered society as necessary for progress and distributes dictatorial philosophy that affects our world, as the Soviet Union and Britain became enemies during World War II.

George Orwell wrote *Animal Farm* as an allegory that was obviously about events that had occurred in the Soviet Union after the 1917 Russian Revolution, with a focus on the Soviet leader, Josef Stalin. Orwell offers a dependable perspective on Russian history and global politics between 1917 and 1943. Orwell composed a political parable to warn against dictatorship and to illustrate what would happen if it were to go uncontrolled. Neither on the farm nor in the community where communism—which was known as animalism—was discovered, according to the historical person and the character in the novel *Animal Farm's* tale. Two pigs died shortly after the narrative began, according to Old Major. Snowball and Napoleon assumed leadership of the farm. The pigs, which Orwell selected as the rebel leaders, were amazing but also somewhat egoistic, impure and lazy animals.

Through the carefully written novel *Animal Farm*, George Orwell demonstrates his literary ability and highlights the terrible crimes of communism, dictatorship, and rebellion. The societies have been destroyed by the course of events. In his study paper "Orwell's *Animal Farm* as a political satire," Didem Baysoy discussed the use of satire and allegory. He also provided illustrations of George Orwell's life and work and discussed his experiences and biography. According to Baysoy, the English society at the start of the 20th century had an impact on the economic and political status of English literature. He wrote about writers of the 20th century who were inspired to write novels about political issues, and the novella *Animal Farm* served as inspiration for Orwell's *Animal Farm*. The question also explains the usage of allegory, including why it was employed and how authors might employ it to tell a story. Furthermore, he included a few authors whose writings included allegories. *Animal Farm's* characterization and the animals' function in representing the humans outside the book were discussed by Baysoy.

The misuse of authority in *Animal Farm* is the subject of this investigation. There will be textual evidence presented to show how the helpless animals on the farm are exploited, either because they are too innocent or because the pigs force them to be. The primary focus of the research will be the language employed by the Soviet authorities to manipulate the common people in 1917. Getting enough evidence from the text will illustrate the function of language as well as the unique importance and worth of Squealer in the story. The purpose of the study is to demonstrate the degree to which the strength of one species—the pigs—benefits all of the farm's animals. The purpose of this parable is to address the subject of whether the pigs' absolute power benefits or enslaves animals by highlighting and discussing the reasons for the pigs' intention to behave like farmer Jones. It could be helpful to comprehend the author's life in order to more fully comprehend the content. Furthermore, providing readers with some historical context from the Russian revolution would help them comprehend the nature of the balance of power in *Animal Farm*. Napoleon was the first example of a single-minded, egoistic, and brutal dictator; he was only in favor of revolution inasmuch as it advanced his despicable desire to rule as the head of the entire animal kingdom. Snowball was a very good speaker; he was fluent and did not think only of himself, but of the good of everybody in life.

Napoleon was not a brilliant talker, but he was smart to gain things for himself. In many ways, Napoleon was the exact opposite of Snowball. While Snowball worked hard to explain the seven commandments to all animals, Napoleon similarly worked hard to distort the same ideology in order to further his own goals. He firmly took full security and squealer.

When Napoleon took full control of the farm, he restored the rights of the animals, imitating Stalin's removing of the Soviet Union during Soviet Russia. "It was noticed that they wagged their tails to him in the same way as the other dogs had been used to do to Mr. Jones"¹ It demonstrates that Napoleon performed just like Mr. Jones, Mr. Jones had particular encouragement for those who led him and underpinned him, but at the time the unfortunate animals rebelled against him, and Napoleon had the dogs who support him when he needed them. A single instance of Napoleon's abuse of power and his taking benefit of the dogs after the animals easily rebelled, he attempted to control those the infant puppies and hiding them so no one knew what had happened to them on the farm, Napoleon's goal at the time was to call his dogs in their private way.

Animal Farm's allegory illustrates that the animals were always symbolic something that the book would convey, such as the presence of animals to the extent of the awful creatures in the novel. The allegory that highlights the comprehension of readers and their ability to identify those symbols while analyzing the misery of the animals was the significant one, except that utilizing animals instead of the seemingly symbolized humans, in many cases we assume that it has represented and determined with human relationship from the creatures to the characters. The primary element of hiding states that writers were terrified of political punishment in their nation when they attempted to express themselves and write a literal genre in a political allegory. When writers criticized the political system, they also made satirical connections to the current topic by subtly drawing attention to similarities.

The effects of World Wars I and II inspired a great number of writers in the contemporary age. Animal Farm was written by George Orwell, one of the greatest novelists, and it was only ten chapters long. Orwell made deliberate remarks about the fascist and communist governments of the 20th century. In this allegory, the protagonists of the Soviet Union—new tyrants of varying degrees—were symbolized by animals, much like any other dictator worldwide.

References:

1. Mariwan Hasan, Lava Muhammad, & Gashbin Bahasin Abuse Practice of Power in Orwell's Animal Farm: A Historical Approach
2. Hirvisaari, J. (2016) "Some Animal Are More Equal than Others"- A Posthumanist Reading of George Orwell's Animal Farm. Diss. Tampere University: Tampere, Apri.
3. Kadečková, T. (2016). Dstopia and Society: George Orwell and Ray Bradbury. Diss

¹ George Orwell, P.35